

iJERResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 3, December- 2024 | Peer-Reviewed
Journal ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14341963

QUALITY INDICATORS AND PARTICIPATORY INSTITUTIONAL EVALUATION: CONTRIBUTIONS TO DEMOCRATIC MANAGEMENT AND INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

AUTHORS

Eliane Maia Miranda Moreira: Master's student in Educational Sciences of the Universidad UNIDA - Paraguay, effective teacher of the municipal education network of Mangaratiba - Rio de Janeiro/Brazil. Director of Basic Education Teaching at the Municipal Secretariat of Education, Sports and Leisure (SMEEL) of Mangaratiba- Rio de Janeiro/Brazil.
Contact: masterseliane2023@gmail.com / 21 – 964013218

Andréia Silva de Miranda: Master's student at the Universidad UNIDA - Paraguay, effective teacher of Early Childhood Education in the municipal education networks of Mangaratiba and Itaguaí - Rio de Janeiro/Brazil. Pedagogical Advisor for Early Childhood Education at the Municipal Department of Education, Sports and Recreation (SMEEL) of Mangaratiba - Rio de Janeiro/Brazil.
Contact: aliceabrahao38@gmail.com / 21 – 964970839

Valeska Regina Soares Marques: Post-Doctorate at the Ibero-American University/PY, PhD in Public Health from the American University; Master in Public Health from the American University, Specialized in Higher Education Teaching; Graduated in Veterinary Medicine from the Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro/Brazil; Graduated in Pedagogy from the Faculty of Philosophy, Sciences and Letters of Boa Esperança .
Contact: valeska_br@hotmail.com / 21 – 972243370

ABSTRACT

Quality Indicators and Participatory Institutional Assessment (AIP), more precisely as diagnostic and planning tools, can help promote school inclusion and consolidate democratization, with a focus on the quality of education. The municipal education network of Mangaratiba/RJ does not yet have participatory institutional assessment as a practice, which limits the participation and voices of parents, students and the school community, the identification of specific areas for improvement, and the challenges in school management. The objective of this research is to understand how Indicators in Participatory Institutional Assessment can contribute to promoting inclusive education, strengthening school management with democratic principles and engaging education stakeholders in improving the quality of education in Mangaratiba/RJ.